

The Impact of Business Ethics and Social Responsibility in Achieving Competitive Advantage: An Empirical Study on Industrial Companies Listed on the Amman Financial Market

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Abstract

This study aims to identify the impact of business ethics and social responsibility in achieving competitive advantage through survey of respondents of managers working in senior management in industrial companies listed on the Amman Stock Exchange. The study population includes all industrial companies listed in the Amman Stock Exchange, shares of (84), The sample contains (65) directors working in senior management in the companies included in the study.

The study finds that there is a statistically significant effect for Business Ethics (independence and objectivity, honesty and integrity, impartiality and transparency) to achieve competitive advantage (lower cost, innovation and renewal) in the Jordanian industrial companies. The results of the study also shows the presence of a statistically significant effect of social responsibility (responsibility towards the environment, responsibility towards consumers, responsibility towards the community) to achieve competitive advantage (lower cost, innovation and renewal) in the Jordanian industrial companies.

The study recommends the development and promotion of business ethics, and the need for the Jordanian industrial companies to identify ethical policies to be distributed across the company, and training of staff to enhance their ability to cope with difficult ethical problems.

Key words: *business ethics, corporate social responsibility, competitive advantage, industrial companies*

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Reference this paper as: Adeb Al Hazaimh , “The Impact of Business Ethics and Social Responsibility in Achieving Competitive Advantage: An Empirical Study on Industrial Companies Listed on the Amman Financial Market” *International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management, Vol. 2, Issue 1, Jan-Feb-2014, pp 66-87,*

INTRODUCTION

The ethical aspects and the need to work in business ethics are not linked to specific communities, but it has become a vital issue however faced by business organizations in developed and developing countries. The concept of ethics related to topics and organizational tasks, resources and human capacities (management and employees, employment, leadership, managers), concept guides and promotes good behavior. This concept has become important for the job in the company and it is confirmed by the administration as it is a self-censorship of the individual because it can distinguish between right and wrong in the behavior at work.

Business ethics relate to the behavior of individuals in various practical activities, this includes the way they deal with their colleagues and customers and anyone else who deals with the company, some find it very difficult to determine where to start one's personal ethics and business ethics, the ethics of personal influence and cover business ethics, and it is important to differentiate between ethical and legal conduct, morality is the expected behavior of individuals, laws are dealing with acts required, there may be legal but immoral or unethical, but not illegal.

CSR is a strategic decision by the Organization and is activated by various activities, Different levels of organizations adopting social responsibility, where some social responsibilities compelled by law, are less than what is required to be applied voluntarily to contribute to a better society.

The extent of the liability is determined by each organization through its social benefit to the community, under the auspices of the social aspects of the environment and contribute to social development and to abandon philosophy maximize profit as a goal, and with responsive business organizations for social responsibility concepts and ideas developed legislation and rules to give these concepts and ideas feature.

The theme of social responsibility of subjects which gains great importance in developed countries long ago, has entered in their plans and awareness campaigns to urge companies to adopt this responsibility and expenditure on this aspect and to assist the government in solving the problems of society.

The theme also has contributed to the global challenges of today, including globalization, increased interest in organizational culture. Human resources have become more responsive to business ethics and social responsibilities in the performance which require completion of the work of the socially responsible individuals and other parties, in the external environment in order to achieve performance expectations of society in general and towards workers.

This research aims to identify the impact of business ethics and social responsibility in achieving competitive advantage through field study in industrial companies listed on Amman financial Market, from the standpoint of departmental senior managers in these companies.

Problem of the research

It is agreed that business organizations are charitable companies and the preoccupation that has been achieved the highest rates of profitability, and the idea should remind corporate social and ethical responsibilities to be profit return on ethically acceptable or legal. Furthermore, the role of the President of the company, being the main source of wealth and employment generation, to carry out their duties according to the modern concepts of social and economic developments, social and environment in an era of rapid change to that too. Hence, this study was represented by her attempt to answer the following questions:

- 1- Is there any impact to business ethics (independence and objectivity, integrity, probity, fairness and transparency) to achieve competitive advantage (cost reduction, innovation and renewal) in Jordanian industrial companies?
- 2- Is there an impact of CSR (responsibility towards the environment, responsibility towards customers, responsibility towards the local community) to achieve competitive advantage (cost reduction, innovation and renewal) in Jordanian industrial companies?

The Aim of the research

This research aims to clarify the overall framework for business ethics and social responsibility and the competitive advantage with different aspects, It aims also to identify the impact of business ethics and social responsibility in achieving competitive advantage through survey respondents from manager's senior management in industrial companies listed on Amman financial Market.

The importance of research

The importance of research lies in its dealing with two important and influential in economic, social, environmental and society: social responsibility and business ethics, and in the light of the studies carried out by the organization making business for social responsibility "in the United States that business organizations that balance their interests and the interests of shareholders had growth rates and rates of generation skilled labor than other companies by four times, it could contribute to the findings of this study in drawing the attention of decision makers in companies In Jordan and in the industrial sector towards the concepts of social responsibility and business ethics to achieve high levels of performance and business organizations in the competitive frameworks.

Model of the study

Figure (1)

The hypotheses of the Research

HO1 no statistically significant effect of business ethics (independence and objectivity, integrity, probity, fairness and transparency) to achieve competitive advantage (cost reduction, innovation and renewal) in Jordanian industrial companies.

HO2 no statistically significant impact of CSR (responsibility towards the environment, responsibility towards customers, responsibility towards the local community) to achieve competitive advantage (cost reduction, innovation and renewal) in Jordanian industrial companies.

Study population

The study population consists of all industrial firms listed in the Amman financial Market (84), (Amman financial Market monthly bulletin and in the month of July 2014), where the distribution of questionnaires to all departmental senior managers in these companies in a comprehensive survey, and recover (69) identification (82.1%) Of the total number of questionnaires sent and sorting through questionnaires, four of which were excluded for incomplete filled out, thus stabilized the sample (65) as Director in the companies included in the study, which analyzed and (77.38%) of the total community.

Unit of analysis and appointed by

To achieve the purpose of the study, the researchers have intended to collect data and information about the current study variables depending on the preview included the directors of companies listed in stock exchange of Amman financial Market.

Sources of data collection

The researcher has adopted two types of information sources. These are the secondary sources such as books and scientific articles, pamphlets and periodicals specialized in the business ethics and social responsibility and the competitive advantage, as reliance on primary sources through the design and development of a special resolution, and to ensure its sincerity and ability to measure the variables of study, has been extracting Cronbakh coefficient Alpha for internal consistency and (83.17%) it is a very good reliable adoption results.

Statistical methods

The researcher using statistical methods in statistical package for social science (SPSS) data analysis where the researchers used averages and standard deviations and multiple linear regression analysis (Multiple Regression) in order to test the hypotheses.

Previous studies

In a study carried out by the Al-taie, in (2006), with a view to developing a conceptual framework for marketing ethics and social responsibility in business organizations. The researcher found that ethics is an environmental impact to the business marketing attention when formulating marketing strategies and pricing strategies and promotion. It also found that the ethics of marketing play a clear role in service marketing mix (7Ps) and reciprocal relationships between business organizations and their customers, and orientation towards knowledge and diagnosis of the wishes and needs of customers for services suited to the wants and needs of access to the detailed service concept to the customer or so-called Customization.

As well as study De Ven (2008), which aimed to develop an ethical framework for corporate social responsibility, companies that have a strong reputation for its customer must use CSR initiatives to achieve their marketing and other immediate objectives. And that specific marketing objectives the company must support up or have a direct link with core values and competitive advantages, and that the company should not try to hide that they benefit from their initiatives in social responsibility.

The results of a study of Hussein, and Al-Jameel, (2009), with the objective of identifying the relationship between the dimensions of social responsibility towards employees and the work ethic, the study found that the concept of social responsibility is one of the concepts that gained attention of most contemporary organizations, which was reflected in the past during the 1960s about maximizing profit at present concept became linked with the social aspect of the organization. The many dimensions of social responsibility towards employees must pay attention to organizations and to achieving the goals and increase their loyalty and interest in the Organization in which they work.

In order to measure the impact of business ethics to ethical conduct and the performance of men's sale of pharmaceutical products in Amman, the study Almrayat (2011) to several findings: that the level of business ethics for the sale of pharmaceutical products in Amman, and the level of ethics for men selling pharmaceuticals in Amman. It also shows a statistically significant direct impact to the business ethics of the Organization on the ethics for men selling pharmaceuticals in Amman.

The study addressed Valentine (2012) training content for business ethics and sales staff from co-workers and supervisors to support organization to high-value business ethics in personal selling, which is further enhanced by the prevailing moral values of the Organization, which leads to the satisfaction of supervisors and employees, they are playing an important role in ethical practice.

Theoretical framework

Ethics is an important pillar and fundamental pillars upon which the communities, is in concept and its role in the social construction of wave and the officer's role beyond the personal to the role of mentor and commanding officer at the social level, and has urged all religions to manners, honest and transparent interaction between people. Play as a morality play in changing human behavior, human behavior is the focus of change in the universe.

They began searching for more speed and impact not only on the globalization, but the impact of economic growth on the social and natural environment in which they live, the organizations operate more and for longer hours and seek to take advantage of economic progress to improve the quality of life in their organizations.

I have had meltdowns and current scandals managers (Helot-Barkerd) and financial fraud and misrepresentation (Enron, WorldCom & Tayco) increased interest in business ethics. Which researchers and practitioners of the sales profession interested particularly in how to take people for ethical decisions in the area of sales, and how exercise might affect organizations in sales practitioners to become more aware and sensitive to ethical issues.

As shown (Low and Weeks), "the need to support and promote ethical behavior is not a subject open to debate". Even when the degree of progressive improvements, organizations can achieve a balance in the efforts to improve business ethics "(Valentine, 2007, p: 248).

the concept of ethics in the business world carries many meaning and contents, revolve mostly around the rules of human behavior, in terms of what is acceptable and not acceptable to others, keeping professionals and researchers in the definition of ethics in terms of content and substance, and that they differed in form and style to business ethics represent moral questions

about what should be and what should not have to perform different types of work (George & Kaler, 2003, p:250).

Ethics reflect a set of rules and principles that determine what is right and wrong behavior, and business ethics is a set of standards and principles that dominate the administrative behavior, and what is right or wrong, they represent guidelines to managers in decision-making and its importance increases proportionally with the effects and consequences of the decision, the more influential Director in the activity, the greater the importance of ethics, Director, ethics is a moral criteria and standards used to discern right from wrong, and business Ethics is a metrics and standards for ethical values and attitudes that govern the decisions and actions that are performed in the working environment (stralsr, 2008, p. 59).

The researcher believes that the concept of ethics is a set of rules and behavioral principles and provisions and the moral values and ethical norms and standards that govern the actions of an individual or group in the performance of work in the work environment, these properties include the independence, objectivity and integrity, probity, fairness, transparency, reliability, responsibility and other aspects of ethical conduct for wrong behavior.

Business ethics

The ethical aspects and the need to work in business ethics by business organizations, are not linked to specific communities, but it has become a vital issue however faced by business organizations in developed and developing countries, the concept of ethics related to topics and organizational tasks, resources and human capacities as management and employees and salesmen and managers, it guides and promotes good behavior, this concept became important for the position in the Organization, as is confirmed by the Administration as it is a self-censorship of the individual, because it can distinguish between right And wrong in his behavior at work, and this is attracting individuals with high work ethics in the Organization on the grounds that these individuals who bring morality or ethics are derived from the Organization's personnel (Daft, 2003, p: 326).

Notes (Valentine & Barnett, 2007) that perceived institutional ethics associated with moral judgments and expectant faith of respondents, and that in order to improve the moral rational

thinking for sale, it is necessary to focus on adherence to ethical issues faced by sale through their work and to deal with the problems of ethical issues in the enterprise.

The current business environment has imposed challenges pushed organizations to invest in activities that are consistent and based on the principles set out by law and moral values, many organizations seek to avoid interrupted by customers, so they are very careful to spare themselves from such positions, which pay more for ethical (Mohr et al. 2001, p. 45).

Has pointed out (Daft, 2003.139: p) that the ethics related to internal values that are part of the cultural environment of the Organization, the moral issue affecting the actions of an individual, group, or organization (negative or positive), while describing (Weihrich & Koontz, 2003, p: 70) work ethic is all about justice and certain aspects such as the community's expectations and competition integrity, advertising and public relations.

Based on the foregoing may be proposing a number of dimensions of social responsibility towards the Organization and personnel within the work ethic:

1. The organization is providing services to employees such as transportation, food, housing and health services.
2. To adopt a specific policy on the management of the participation of workers in the profits of the Organization, and the adoption of an administrative policy allowing individuals to participate in decision-making processes (stralsr, 2008, p. 68).
3. rewards and incentives for personnel in accordance with the principle of efficiency and merit, and that the organization is working to honor and encourage outstanding personnel and creators, as well as workers ' compensation for injuries or occupational diseases in the industrial organizations (stralsr, 2008, p. 68).
4. Development and implementation of awareness programmers for personnel include important standards adopted at the social, environmental and safety in the workplace.
5. to raise the morale of workers and spread the spirit of cooperation and motivation, motivation and retaining them and prevent their infiltration to reduce unemployment and reduce the

problems of absenteeism, turnover, accidents at work, and provide an opportunity for young people.

6. Try to develop specific actions to limit the use of personnel resources of the Organization and its uses for personal and adoption program, a model for ethical conduct for dealing practices of employees related to personal considerations such as fairness, prejudice, favoritism.

7. Follow-up of the personnel regarding all practices on illegal agreements or for the Organization, and safeguard the rights of individuals in the Organization as part of the community.

Social responsibility

Various definitions of the concept of social responsibility in the underpinnings and implications, according to the nature of the work and material and human capabilities and the surrounding environment, regulations and legislation which govern and regulate their work.

Both have pointed out (Carter & Burritt, 2007, p:19) to try to find a definition of the concept of social responsibility, which emerged in different names all point to social responsibility (social accountability and organizational ethics and organizational citizenship and organizational commitments), is a difficult as this term or concept is complicated, like the term globalization and sustainable development, these terms have multiple meanings, so that if one appears reflected a new understanding of the concept or term.

In view of the increasing importance of social responsibility have appeared many definitions that tried to determine the precise definition of social responsibility, notably the definition of ISO international standards organization, known as: "the Organization's responsibility for the consequences of its decisions and activities on society and the environment through transparency and ethical behavior consistent with sustainable development and the well-being of the community as well as taking into account the expectations of shareholders, social responsibility is a commitment to work towards the community in which it operates, by contributing to a wide range of social activities such as combating poverty, improving Health services, combating pollution, and create jobs and solve the problem of housing and transportation, among others.

Finds (Asongu, 2007, p:2) that social responsibility is the commitment of the owners of the economic activities contribute to sustainable development by working with the local community, with the aim of improving the standard of living of the population in a serving of economy and development, and the developmental role of the private sector should be initiated internally and momentum from within the decision-makers in the enterprise, CSR can be defined in a general sense as the relationship between the Organization and the community that are in scope, focusing on the commitments The Organization must meet if it is to be considered with the qualities of good citizenship.

Based on the concept of social responsibility to participate in economic activities sustainable in nature, go beyond legal requirements to protect the welfare of employees and the community and environment, and strategically can create tangible material benefits for the Organization, and thus the ability to fund projects or initiatives themselves and at the same time reduce the objection the shareholders on waste their wealth and social responsibility emphasizing sustainability and human elements, environmental sustainability include the use of scientific ideas that work to reduce the adverse environmental effects of the operations of the Organization, and cosmic issues as declining resources and energy Non-renewable and handling of waste from manufacturing processes and human consumption, sustainability, based on creating a healthy work environment and fair to the staff, and the development of abilities and skills and add benefit to the stakeholders of customers and suppliers and other community members (Heslin and Ochoa, 2008, p:126-p: 127).

The competitive advantage

The concept of competitive advantage has filled space and an important place in each of the areas of strategic management and business economics (Betlis, 2000, p: 7), the competitive advantage of the important strategic element to help capture opportunities, offers substantial and genuine opportunity to achieve sustained profit organization compared to its competitors. It is the source of competitiveness and strengthen the company's position in its economic benefits, through their competitors in the areas of product, price, cost, and therefore focus on production.

Studies show (Covin, 2000, p: 175) to competitive advantages is a specific property or group of properties owned by the Organization and to distinguish them from others, so check out her

strong stance against various parties. And that the real challenge facing any organization not to produce or deliver products, but constant saturation capacity to the needs and wishes of the customers. The growing role of customers and became difficult to enforce product, thus creating competitive advantages in its products would achieving client satisfaction, increase their loyalty and ability of survival and persistence in the market.

And both (Macmillan & Mahan, 2001, p: 81) the competitive advantage is a property or group of properties or component than for its unique organization, enabling it to keep for a relatively long period of time as a result of the difficulty of replicating, check out this period her benefit and to outdo competitors in their products to customers.

And once the competitive advantage created by the Organization to employ new methods more effective than those used by competitors, and they come through and develop new services through the learning capabilities and market supervision. Asserts (Stevenson, 2007, p: 4) that a competitive advantage is designed to meet the needs and desires of customers to acquire the product or service. And the competitive advantage created by the Organization to discover new methods is more effective than those employed by competitors.

The competitive advantage is skill or technique or outstanding resource which enables the Organization production values and benefits for customers than its competitors, and confirms their uniqueness and different from those of competitors, from the point of view of customers who accept this difference and distinction, so bring them more benefits and values that outperforms the others by their competitors.

Data analysis and hypothesis testing

The first hypothesis test:

HO1 no statistically significant effect of business ethics (independence and objectivity, integrity, probity, fairness and transparency) to achieve competitive advantage (cost reduction, innovation and renewal) in Jordanian industrial companies.

Table (2)

Arithmetic averages and deviations of the first premise (business ethics)

Number	The term	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Order by relevance
Independence and objectivity				
1	Impartiality and neutrality in the course of business	4.2000	0.7978	3
2	Resistance to side effects when you do the work	4.2125	0.7867	2
3	Avoid any relationships may appear to lose objectivity and independence when you do business	4.3050	0.7337	1
Honesty and integrity				
4	Honesty and integrity, taking into account the balance of interests	4.0675	0.8887	6
5	Professional capacity to improve work and workmanship and keeping secrets	3.6250	1.1056	9
6	Honesty, integrity and aligned to the company's interest	3.8600	0.9735	8
Integrity and transparency				
7	Integrity and chastity on-the-job	4.0700	0.8899	5
8	Exercise of Justice at work	3.8700	0.9876	7
9	To be honest in performing duties	4.1300	0.9166	4
	Overall average	4.0377	0.8978	

Can be seen from table 2 that the arithmetic was (4.0377). By comparing the obtained average measurement tool used to measure this variable, it can be seen that the highest point that represents the degree of approval (+ 4), standard deviation (0.8978). According to the results, **"there is a statistically significant effect of business ethics (independence and objectivity, integrity, probity, fairness and transparency) to achieve competitive advantage (cost reduction, innovation and renewal) in Jordanian industrial corporations"**. The answers ranged between (4.3050) paragraph (3) and highest percentage of responses, this paragraph provides that "avoid any relationships may appear to lose objectivity and independence when you do." Paragraph (5), got the lowest record, averaging (3.8694), this paragraph provides that "the professional capacity to improve work and workmanship and keeping secrets".

Using multiple regression analysis the following table no. 3 shows the results obtained when testing the hypothesis.

Table (3): Multiple regression test results to influence business ethics

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	F	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	-0.069	0.096		-0.719	0.473
Business ethics	0.942	0.023	0.897	40.508	0.000

R= 0.897 R²= 0.805

According to data in table (3) to the calculated F values for this hypothesis (40.508) is greater than the value of F indexed (1. 645), so that the resolution refers to a the nihilistic premise rejected if the calculated F value is greater than the F scale, it is accepting the alternative hypothesis, which States **"a statistically significant effect of business ethics (independence and objectivity, integrity, probity, fairness and transparency) to achieve competitive advantage (cost reduction, innovation and renewal) in Jordanian industrial corporations"**, and this is confirmed by Value semantics (Sig) of zero as it is less than 5%. Note that the

coefficient (Beta) was referring to the tendency of 0.897 relationship whereby between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

The second hypothesis test:

HO2 no statistically significant impact of CSR (responsibility towards the environment, responsibility towards customers, responsibility towards the local community) to achieve competitive advantage (cost reduction, innovation and renewal) in Jordanian industrial companies.

Table (4): Arithmetic averages and deviations of the second premise (social responsibility)

Number	The term	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Order by relevance
Responsibility towards the environment				
10	Participation in environmental protection programmers	4.1050	0.9624	5
11	Linking environmental performance to the company's mission and vision	4.4175	0.7935	1
12	Beautify the surrounding area and the afforestation for conservation of the environment	3.8625	1.0228	9
Responsibility towards customers				
13	The company offers products at affordable prices	4.1525	0.8251	4
14	The company's eagerness to make products easy to obtain by consumers	4.2125	0.8391	2

15	The company's eagerness to make products safe when you use	3.8699	0.9228	8
Responsibility towards the local community				
16	The company provided contributions or donations for the benefit of the community	4.1925	0.8167	3
17	Company-provided material support to religious and national events in the community	4.0100	0.9010	6
18	Funding for the enterprise community	3.8711	0.9228	7
	Overall average	4.1360	0.8801	

Show that the arithmetic total (4.1360) by comparing the obtained average measurement tool used to measure this variable indicates that more than the point represents the degree of approval (+ 4), standard deviation (0.8801). According to these results, **there is a statistically significant effect for social responsibility (responsibility towards the environment, responsibility towards customers, responsibility towards the local community) to achieve competitive advantage (cost reduction, innovation and renewal) in Jordanian industrial corporations "**. The answers ranged between (4.4175) paragraph (11) and the highest percentage of responses, this paragraph provides that "linking environmental performance to the company's mission and vision." Paragraph (12), got the lowest record, averaging (3.8694), this paragraph provides that the "beautify the surrounding area and forested to preserve the environment."

Using simple regression analysis the following table 5 shows the results obtained when testing the hypothesis.

Table (5):Multiple regression test results (Multiple Regression) to effect social responsibility

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	F	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	-0.063	0.109		-0.581	0.562
Social responsibility	0.919	0.026	0.8720	35.482	0.000

R= 0.872 R²= 0.760

According to data in table (5) to the calculated F values for this hypothesis (35.482), which is greater than the value of F indexed (1. 645) as the base resolution refers to reject null hypothesis if the calculated F value is greater than the F scale, and accordingly it is accepting the alternative hypothesis, which States "**a statistically significant effect for social responsibility (responsibility towards the environment, responsibility towards customers, responsibility towards the local community) to achieve competitive advantage (cost reduction, innovation) in enterprises Jordan industrial**", and this is confirmed by value semantics (Sig) of zero as it is less than 5%. Note that the coefficient (Beta) was referring to the tendency for 0.8720 relationship whereby between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Results dependent variable: competitive advantage

Table (6)

Arithmetic averages and deviations of the dependent variable: competitive advantage

Number	The term	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Order by relevance
Cost reduction				
19	The cost of the materials used in our products is low in comparison with	4.0675	0.81523	3

	competitors			
20	Business ethics and social responsibility to help the company reduce costs continuously direct industrial	3.9500	0.89695	5
21	Business ethics and social responsibility to help the company reduce costs and maintenance operations	4.2030	0.81530	1
Innovation and renewal				
22	Business ethics and social responsibility help to provide new products to simulate changing market needs	4.1575	0.88581	2
23	Business ethics and social responsibility, help in the research and development efforts for the development of its products	3.8975	0.86537	6
24	Business ethics and social responsibility help to develop products based on market studies	4.0300	0.83717	4
	Overall average	4.0509	0.8526	

Show that the arithmetic total (4.0509) comparing the obtained average measurement tool used to measure this variable indicates that more than the point represents the degree of approval (+ 4), standard deviation (0.8526). The answers ranged between (4.2030) paragraph (21), which got the highest percentage of responses, this paragraph provides that "business ethics and social

responsibility to help the company reduce costs and maintenance operations. Paragraph (23), got the lowest record, averaging (3. 681), this paragraph provides that "business ethics and social responsibility, help in the research and development efforts for the development of its products.

Results

1. The results of the study showed a statistically significant effect of business ethics (independence and objectivity, integrity, probity, fairness and transparency) to achieve competitive advantage (cost reduction, innovation and renewal) in Jordanian industrial companies. The results showed that companies based on business ethics is keen to avoid any relationships may appear to lose objectivity and independence when you do business, working on the resistance side effects when you do the work and thinking and impartiality in the performance of the business and, as keen on honesty and integrity and respect the balance of interests and biases in the interest of the company and the business ethics increase their professional improvement and mastery and keeping secrets, as well as showing the importance of being honest and integrity and chastity on-the-job, in addition To be fair when you do.
2. The results of the study showed a statistically significant effect for social responsibility (responsibility towards the environment, responsibility towards customers, responsibility towards the local community) to achieve competitive advantage (cost reduction, innovation and renewal) in Jordanian industrial companies. The results showed that corporate social responsibility of linking environmental performance to its mission and has engaged in environmental protection and beautification of the surrounding area and forested to preserve the environment, it turns out that companies eager to make products easy to obtain by consumers, honest products when in use and they offer products at affordable prices. As well as showing corporate contributions or donations for the benefit of the community and provides material support to religious and national events in the local community, in addition to providing funding for the community.

Recommendations

1. Develop and promote business ethics, the need for Jordanian industrial companies with ethical policies and distributed across the company, and the training of staff to enhance their ability to cope with difficult ethical problems.
2. The attention of the Jordanian industrial companies with objectivity and independence and the ability to take account of the balance of interests, and the ability to work and mastery.
3. Emphasize the importance of fairness and transparency to ensure neutrality and distance from any side effects, impact on competitive advantage from the point of view of the study sample.
4. Work to find and activate the codes of ethics for the environment and commitment from everyone.
5. The Jordanian industrial companies to make products safe and risk-free when you use the products and instructions required.
6. Underlining the importance of the Jordanian industrial companies with the support of civil society institutions, and increase its contribution to the establishment of educational centers, recreational and healthy.
7. The need to understand and study and analysis of the constituent elements of morality and social responsibility as one of the most important pillars to ensure the company's success and longevity, especially in view of the diversity and complexity and the complexity of its risks.
8. Work on the development of curricula (ethics) in State and private universities that teach business management.

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